

An Approximation of Daily Rainfall by Using a Pixel Value Data Approach

Authors : Sarisa Pinkham, Kanyarat Bussaban

Abstract : The research aims to approximate the amount of daily rainfall by using a pixel value data approach. The daily rainfall maps from the Thailand Meteorological Department in period of time from January to December 2013 were the data used in this study. The results showed that this approach can approximate the amount of daily rainfall with RMSE=3.343.

Keywords : daily rainfall, image processing, approximation, pixel value data

Conference Title : ICMCSSE 2014 : International Conference on Mathematical, Computational and Statistical Sciences and Engineering

Conference Location : Tokyo, Japan

Conference Dates : May 29-30, 2014